

Studies on desulphurisation of epithio derivatives of isomeric aleuritic acid and their corresponding dihydroxy dioic acids

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(Z) and (E)-Epithio derivatives of isomeric aleuritic acids (9,10,16-trihydroxyhexadecanoic) and 9,10-dihydroxyhexadecane-1,16-dioic acids have been synthesised. Their desulphurisation with iodine yielded corresponding unsaturated acids without any change in configuration.

Desulphurisation of organic compounds has recently gained increasing attention in two quite diverse fields, namely, synthetic fuels and organic syntheses¹. In the former area, the production of environmentally acceptable fuels from coal or petroleum involves the removal of bound sulphur such as sulfides or mercaptans, from final product. In the latter area, organic synthetic methodology currently utilises a variety of sulphur containing groups to achieve a broad range of selective reactions, but after the reaction the adjuvant sulphur group must be removed².

These prompted us to study desulphurisation reaction of hitherto unreported epithio derivatives of isomeric aleuritic acid (9,10,16-trihydroxyhexadecanoic acid, the major constituent acid of shellac (yield ~35%) obtained by its alkaline hydrolysis³) and their corresponding dihydroxydioic acids for the removal of vicinal hydroxyl groups at C-9 and C-10 positions. The resulting alkenoic acids have been used for the syntheses of macrocyclic ketones and lactones⁴⁻⁶ having musk-like odour such as civetone (cycloheptadecanone), exaltone (cyclopentadecanone) and (E)-9-hexadecenolide (isoambrettolide). Isoambrettolide is being used as a fixative in perfumery industry.

erythro-Aleuritic acid on treatment with conc. HCl for 6 h followed by the hydrolysis of the resulting product with alc. NaOH⁷ yielded (Z)-9,10-epoxy-16-hydroxyhexadecanoic acid. Treatment of the epoxy acid with thiourea solution in dioxane afforded (Z)-9,10-epithio-16-hydroxyhexadecanoic acid, which on desulphurisation with iodine solution in benzene furnished 16-hydroxy-(Z)-9-hexadecenoic acid.

Similarly, *erythro*-9,10-dihydroxyhexadecane-1,16-dioic acid (prepared from *threo*-9,10-dihydroxy-1,16-dioic acid following the method of Chatterjea *et al.*⁸ was converted to (Z)-9,10-epoxyhexadecane-1,16-dioic acid, which on treatment with thiourea solution afforded (Z)-9,10-epithiohexadecane-1,16-dioic acid. Its desulphurisation with iodine gave the desired (E)-9-hexadecenedioic acid.

threo-Aleuritic and *threo*-9,10-dihydroxyhexadecane-1,16-dioic acids furnished corresponding (E)-epithioacids. Their desulphurisation with iodine solution in benzene also afforded 16-hydroxy-(E)-9-hexadecenoic and (E)-9-hexadecene-1,16 dioic acid respectively (vide Experimental).

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer, ¹H NMR spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 instrument and ¹³C NMR spectra on a Varian XL-100 spectrometer with fourier transform attached to a computer device. Chemical shifts (δ, ppm) are reported relative to TMS as an internal reference. Purity of the compounds were routinely checked by TLC on silica gel G. For column chromatography silica gel (100-200 mesh) was used.

(Z)-9,10-Epoxy-16-hydroxy hexadecanoic acid : erythro-Aleuritic acid⁸ (m.p. 124–23°, 5 g) was converted to titled acid as a solid (3 g) m.p. 60–62° (lit.⁹, m.p. 60–61°) following the reported procedure⁸; ν_{\max} 3250 (OH), 1700 (COOH), 890 cm^{-1} (-CH-CH-); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃)

3.2 (2H, br, m,) (Found : C, 67.0; H, 10.4. calcd.

for: C₁₆H₃₀O₄ : C, 67.1; H, 10.5%).

(Z)-9,10-Epithio-16-hydroxy hexadecanoic acid : A solution of the foregoing epoxy acid (3.5 g) in dioxane (10 ml) was slowly added to the thioiurea solution (thioiurea (1 g) in H₂O (10 ml)) and conc. H₂SO₄ (d, 1.84; 0.2 ml) and left overnight. Aq. NaHCO₃ solution (10 ml; 25%), then added to reaction mixture maintained at 40° for 1 h. Acidification of the cooled mixture yielded a solid, which was purified by column chromatography. Elution with pet. ether (40–60°)-ether (95 : 5; v/v) gave white needles of the desired compound (2.2 g), m.p. 72–74°; ν_{\max} 3250 (OH), 1705 (CO), 595 cm^{-1} (-CH-CH-); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) 0.87 (3H, t

CH₂CH₃), 1.3 (2OH, 10 × CH₂, bs), 7.05 (2H, m (Z)) (Found : C, 60.2; H, 9.1; S, 10.4. C₁₆H₃₀O₃S

requires : C, 60.3; H, 9.2; S, 10.6%).

16-Hydroxy-(Z)-9-hexadecenoic acid¹² : A solution of (Z)-9,10-epithio-16-hydroxyhexadecanoic acid (2 g) in benzene (10 ml) was added slowly to a boiling solution of iodine (2 g) in benzene (10 ml) over a period of 30 min and heated under reflux for 2 h. Benzene was then removed in vacuo and aq. sodium thiosulphate (5%) was added to the reaction mixture till the colour discharged. On usual work-up with ether, a thick liquid was obtained which was purified by column chromatography. Elution with 20% ethylacetate in benzene afforded the desired enoic acid as a colourless thick oil (1.3 g); ν_{\max} (neat) 3250 (-OH), 1700 (-COOH), 752 cm^{-1} (Z HC=CH); ¹H NMR (CCl₄) 2.26 (2H, t, CH₂COOH), 3.56 (2H, t, CH₂OH), 5.26 (2H, t, Z CH=CH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) 179.31 (C=O of carboxyl at C-1), 130.3 and 130.5 (two Z olefinic carbons at C-9 and C-10 respectively), 75.31 (-CH₂OH at C-15), 31.27, 25.39, 24.43 (methylene carbons)¹³ (Found : C, 71.2; H, 11.1. Calcd. for C₁₆H₃₀O₃ : C, 71.1; H, 11.1%).

(Z)-9,10-Epoxy-hexadecane-1,16-dioic acid : erythro-9,10-Dihydroxyhexadecane-1,16-dioic acid (m.p. 149–50°, 4.0 g) was converted into (Z)-epoxy dioic acid as a solid (2.8 g, m.p. 60–62°) (lit.⁹ m.p. 60–61°); ν_{\max} 1700 (COOH),

890 cm^{-1} (-CH-CH-); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) 3.2 (2H, br, m, Z,

) (Found : C, 63.9; H, 9.2. Calcd. for C₁₆H₂₈O₅ : C, 64.0; H, 9.3%).

(Z)-9,10-Epithio-hexadecane-1,16-dioic acid : Similar treatment of the above epoxy-dioic acid (1 g) in dioxane (4 ml) with thiourea solution and usual work-up afforded (Z)-epithioacid as a solid (0.5 g, m.p. 136–38°) (ethyl acetate); ν_{\max} 1700 (COOH), 592 cm^{-1} (-CH-CH-); ¹H NMR

(CDCl₃) 2.9 (2H, m, Z,) (Found : C, 60.5; H, 9.1, S, 10.0. C₁₆H₂₈O₄S requires : C, 60.5; H, 9.1; S, 10%).

(Z)-9-Hexadecne-1,16-dioic acid : Following the procedure described for (Z)-9,10-epoxy-hexadecane-1,16-dioic acid, the title compound was obtained as a solid (0.34 g), m.p. 97–98° (ethyl acetate) from the foregoing epithiodioic acid (0.5 g); ν_{\max} 1710 (COOH), 970 cm^{-1} (Z; HC=CH) ¹H NMR (CDCl₄) 5.27 cm^{-1} (2H, m, (Z CH=CH) (Found : C, 67.5; H, 9.7. C₁₆H₂₈O₄ requires : C, 67.6; H, 9.8%).

(E)-9,10-Epoxy-16-hydroxyhexadecanoic acid : threo-Aleuritic acid (5 g, m.p. 100–101°) was converted to the desired epoxy acid as a solid (3.5 g), m.p. 72–73°, following the reported procedure⁸ (Found : C, 67.1; H, 10.3. Calcd. for C₁₆H₃₀O₄ : C, 67.1; H, 10.4%). It was further characterized by IR and ¹H NMR spectra.

(E)-9,10-Epithio-16-hydroxyhexadecanoic acid : The title acid was obtained as a solid (0.7 g, m.p. 84–86°) (acetone) from (E)-9,10-epoxy-16-hydroxyhexadecanoic acid (1.0 g); ν_{\max} 3250 (OH), 1700 (COOH), 592 cm^{-1} (-CH-CH-); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) 2.65 (2H, m, (E,)

(Found : C, 60.1; H, 10.0; S, 10.5. C₁₆H₃₀O₃S requires : C, 60.2; H, 9.9; S, 10.5%).

(E)-9,10-Epoxyhexadecane-1,16-dioic acid : This was obtained as a solid (0.6 g, m.p. 82–84°) (lit.⁹ m.p. 82–83°) from threo-9,10-dihydroxyhexadecane-1,16-dioic acid (1 g) (Found : C, 64.0; H, 9.1. Calcd. for C₁₆H₂₈O₅ : C, 64.0; H, 9.3%; ν_{\max} 1705 (COOH), 890 cm^{-1} (-CH-CH-); ¹H NMR

(CDCl₃) 2.75 (2H, t, Z,)

16-Hydroxy-(E)-9-hexadecenoic acid : The above epithio acid (2.0) on desulphurisation with iodine yielded a solid (1.5 g, m.p. 68–70°) (lit.⁹ m.p. 66–68°) ν_{\max} 3250, 970 cm^{-1} (E CH=CH); δ (CCl₄) 2.27 (2H, t, CH₂COOH),

3.55 (2H, t, CH₂OH), 5.26 (2H, t, Z CH=CH).

(*E*)-9,10-Epithiohexadecane-1,16-dioic acid : The desired epithiodioic acid was obtained as a solid (0.62 g, m.p. 152–154°) (from acetone) from (*E*)-9,10-epoxy-hexadecane-1,16-dioic acid (1.0 g), adopting the procedure described earlier; ν_{\max} 1705 (COOH), 582 cm⁻¹ (-CH-CH-); ¹H NMR

2.6 (2H, m, (*E*, -CH-CH-)) (Found : C, 60.0; H, 9.0; S,

10.5. C₁₆H₂₈O₄S requires : C, 60.2; H, 8.8; S, 10.6%).

(*E*)-9-Hexadecene-1,16-dioic acid : This was obtained as a solid (0.36 g, m.p. 102–103°) (ethyl acetate) (lit.¹¹ m.p. 102–103°) from (*E*)-9,10-epithio-hexadecane-1,16-dioic acid (0.5 g) following the procedure reported earlier; ν_{\max} 1700 (COOH), 970 cm⁻¹ (Z HC=CH); ¹H NMR (CCl₄) 5.3 (2H, m, Z CH=CH).

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